

Challenges in promoting Bangenge Festival in Cavite City

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Abstract

The Bangenge Festival is a traditional festival celebrated and a parade that presents various mascots in Cavite City and its surrounding areas which is held every mid-December. The objectives of this study are to promote the Bangenge Festival as a cultural tourism attraction and to identify the challenges of promoting it. The target populations were the tourism officials, students, teachers, tourists and residents of the destination. A descriptive research design is employed. Non-probability sampling was employed to obtain the right respondents. Thus, 31 respondents were chosen through snowball sampling technique and were given a survey questionnaire. Findings show that most of the respondents are in favor of promoting the festival in another location. They think that having competition that involves schools and other institutions may help promote the Bangenge Festival more and agreed that the said festival still promotes its history, conserving tradition and its location.

Keywords: Bangenge; Bangenge Festival; Cultural Tourism; Festival; Traditions.

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Introduction

The Bangenge Festival is a parade featuring large mascots that takes place in Cavite City during the middle of December. It actually became a tradition for children in the city to go caroling with a dancing paper mascot (Lutong Cavite, 2013). It has been celebrating the Bangenge Festival since the 1970s. Bangenge Festival is one of the Christmas traditions, alongside gift giving and eating foods such as bibingka and puto bumbong, which everyone always looks for during the said festivity. The appearance of a Bangenge is free-form, meaning that anyone can create or design any character they imagine, whether it be an anime, Marvel, DC, celebrity, movie, TV, or gaming character (Riego de Dios, 2015). This shows Caviteños' creativity and ingenuity, which is more like a Christmas tradition in their city where different representatives from schools and barangays participate in a grand parade. Mascots made for the Bangenge Festival are heavy. The festival was called as such because every time the mascots move, they seem to be like a drunk person. Also, it was a tradition of Caviteños where one of the contestants wore paper materials and became a mascot.

In its early years, the mascot's base was typically made from 'kaing' or fruit and vegetable baskets discarded in the public market. As time goes on, some create their own symbols. This is done to make the mascots appear larger, stronger, and more flexible. It was also used during caroling, dancing to the beat of 'tambols' or snare drums made from tin cans, rubber bands, and used umbrella fabric. The drumstick is produced from a barbecue stick, a cigar butt, and rubber bands, while the bass drum is created from used water containers.

It has a contest named '*Pasiklaban ng mga Bangenge*' that typically begins every second week of December. All the Bangenges will be on display for several days before the grand parade. In this context, every participant is investing a lot of effort into their work, and some even spend months creating their mascots. Bangenge Festival is only known by the locals of Cavite City even though it is paraded in the towns of Kawit and Noveleta. With this, the researchers decided to conduct a study to determine why the festival is unpopular and identify the challenges in promoting the Bangenge Festival.

Review of Related Literature

Events and festivals are important parts of the tourism product in many destinations (Getz and Page, 2016). Aside from food and souvenirs, events and festivals are two of the reasons why tourists flock to a certain destination. According to Mair and Whitford (2013), the ability of festivals and events to draw visitors to a host area and to support its economic and social development explains why they are given much importance in many tourism policies and strategies.

Ramya (2019) stated that cultural tourism is the fastest-growing part of the tourism industry, leading to a trend of increasing specialization among tourists. Festivals are short periods of celebration that have a specific purpose connected to different parts of tribal life. It is a time of rest from difficult daily tasks, allowing people to enjoy leisure time and engage with the cultural activities and entertainment offered by the event.

Pasya et al. (2016) mentioned that there are many reasons that motivate people to travel to places outside their usual destinations. Their journey creates economic opportunities for the local population at their destination. Therefore, the community may enhance their income and overall well-being. Not only does it boost the economy, but tourism also helps promote local values and sustainable practices. Cultural motivation involves taking part in traditional festivals and events, experiencing the daily activities of the community, observing artifacts and architectural features, and other similar activities. In this way, the community indirectly encourages the preservation of their culture and the transmission of these values to future generations.

Wu and Ai (2016) noted that festivals and events are significant tourism resources. Tourists visit a host community and destinations to attend festivals and events. Tourism contributes significantly to the economic development of the local communities where it takes place (Ui et al., 2013). Hosting festivals and events in local communities is a common strategy for promoting tourism development. It attracts tourists to the tourism destination, creates job opportunities related to tourism, and distributes economic benefits throughout the destination (Abba and Abubakar, 2019; Ololo & Dieke, 2022).

Skoultos (2014) discovered that festivals and culture are closely associated with each other. Social changes and globalization are considered the primary factors contributing to the rapid growth of festivals throughout the 20th century. Celebrating festivals keeps the culture alive. Tanford and Jung (2017) mentioned that festivals help in maintaining local cultural traditions, supporting tourism, and promoting economic, social, and cultural developments in the area where the festival takes place. Although festivals can have positive impacts on a destination, the arrival of many tourists may also lead to some negative consequences (Csapo, 2012).

Finkel and Platt (2020) noted that cities have traditionally served as centers for celebration and festivity, bringing people together as a way to take a break from the usual routine of daily life. Festivals have frequently acted as connections between people and locations, linking individual experiences with shared cultural moments, making them more important for cultural geographers. However, festivals also have social, economic, and political elements that are influenced by society and context of the time and place. Nowadays, contemporary cultural festivals often reveal complex and uncomfortable tensions between the socio-economic strategies of commercialized neoliberal cities and the cultural needs of various communities to come together and celebrate. Cultural festivals and cities maintain an ongoing relationship, which is now primarily commercialized and politicized, having diverse impacts on communities, urban spaces, and cultural identities.

According to Ngernyuang and Wu (2020), which examined how social media factors influence festival tourism and also serve as a tool for promoting it, the findings indicate that social media is more effectively used as a search engine. They also mentioned that the growth of the internet has transformed the world, and with the vast amount of information online, people can quickly find the information they need. Prior to this one, people typically use media as part of their daily activities, staying connected with their online friends and sharing photos and videos from their travels. People became interested to read more comments on that post, which made them want to join that festival. They looked for specific information online regarding the festival, the expenses involved, and the important factors they should know before joining. In the set of analyzed research papers, the literature on cultural studies, cultural festivals, and cultural tourism have been investigated, particularly in examining the challenges in promoting a festival, where festivals are celebrations of life, bringing peace and joy to humanity and breaking the monotony of life.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers used descriptive research design, which aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. Survey questionnaires were used to collect the data that were required for the study. It helps the research to aim and identify characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Cavite City. Mostly, they celebrated the festival at the Cavite National High School after they parade their giant mascots, where they gathered all the mascots to prepare and perform for a contest. Thirty-one (31) respondents composed of students, teachers, and tourists who were able to attend the festival were included. The researchers used snowball sampling in which respondents are asked to assist researchers in identifying other potential subjects; it was utilized to help the researchers identify the respondents who were able to attend the festival.

Research Instrument

The researchers used survey questionnaires to gather data and conduct informative evaluation. Survey questionnaires were used to gather descriptive information on challenges in promoting the Bangenge Festival in Cavite City. Survey questionnaires that are being used were self-made and are based from the assumptions and gathered ideas from related studies.

The survey consists of nine (9) questions that are focused on knowing current status of the festival, the programs or activities that can be developed to promote Bangenge Festival in Cavite City, the history on how the Bangenge festival was originated, on providing the opportunities for different cultures to interact with one another, and also focuses on helping to strengthen the city tourism industry, the participation of tourists and locals in the program and in the materials used in making the mascots help attracts the tourists and the locals. The survey used was the subject to help emphasize and know the place better. Our study utilized questionnaires that were approved by a faculty member. Questionnaires were highly practical and could be carried out by any number of people, moreover the results could be quickly quantified. Over the years, gathering information through questionnaires has been proven to be more scientifically accurate. In addition, our instrument made use of a 5-point Likert scale.

Data Collection and Analysis

To obtain the data, the researchers distributed the Likert scale survey questionnaires to the respondents. For the tourists, snowball sampling was utilized to help the researchers identify the respondents who were able to attend the festival. Snowball sampling is beneficial when there is limited prior knowledge about the topic or issue. It is utilized due to its cost-effectiveness, simplicity, and efficiency.

The data analysis used in this study is a descriptive statistic to gather and conduct informative evaluation from the survey questionnaire we have gathered. The data was systematically tabulated, analyzed and interpreted by the researchers in order to obtain accurate information and figures to this analysis. Furthermore, the following verbal interpretation was used on the survey questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale:

- Strongly Agree (5)
- Agree (4)
- Neutral (3)
- Disagree (2)
- Strongly Disagree (1)

Percentage is a number or ratio expressed as a fraction of 100, it means parts per hundred. The researchers used this survey because it examines the percentage of affirmative responses compared to the total responses received. To calculate the survey percentage, basic division is required, and data should be organized to allow researchers to quickly sum affirmative responses and exclude non-affirmative ones.

A weighted definition is used to calculate the average amount of data. The purpose of this is to calculate the weighted value where the data is presented differently compared to the definition of arithmetic or mean sample. The weighted means and interpretations are as follows:

- 4.23 – 5.00: Strongly Agree
- 3.42 – 4.22: Agree
- 2.62 – 3.41: Neutral
- 1.81 – 2.61: Disagree
- 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents (N = 31)

Profile	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20 and below	28	90.32%
	21-30	3	9.68%
Gender	Female	27	87.10%
	Male	4	12.90%
Monthly Income	Below 10,000	1	3.23%
	10,001-20,000	3	9.68%
	20,001-40,000	4	12.90%
	40,001-60,000	2	6.45%
	Not applicable	21	67.74%
Civil Status	Single	31	100.00%

Table 1 reveals the demographic profile of the respondents. Based on the result of the survey with 31 respondents, in terms of age, 90.32% of the respondents are from ages 20 and below, while the remaining 9.68% belong to the age range 21 to 30 years old. In terms of gender, 87.1% of the respondents are female and the remaining 12.9% are male. In terms of monthly income, the result shows that 67.74% of the respondents have answered 'not applicable' as their family monthly income; 12.9% of the respondents have 20,001 to 40,000 PhP monthly income; 9.68% answered 10,000 to 20,000 PhP as their monthly income; 6.45% of the respondents have a monthly income of 40,001 to 60,000 PhP; and the remaining 3.23% have a monthly income of their family below 10,000 PhP. In terms of civil status, it shows that all of the respondents are single.

Table 2. Level of Perceptions in Bangenge Festival

Perceptions	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Bangenge mascots represent the intended characters.	4.00	Agree
2. The history still advocates how the Bangenge Festival originated.	4.21	Agree
3. Bangenge Festival helps to emphasize and know the place better.	4.16	Agree
4. Bangenge Festival provides opportunity for different cultures to interact with one another.	4.09	Agree
5. Bangenge Festival helps in strengthening the city's tourism industry.	4.16	Agree
6. There is enticement of the tourists and locals to participate in the program.	4.16	Agree
7. The materials used in making the mascots help attract tourists and locals to participate in the festival.	4.12	Agree
8. The respondents want to recommend this event.	4.12	Agree
Total	4.13	Agree

Table 2 indicates the level of perceptions in Bangenge Festival. The data show an overall positive view of the Bangenge Festival, with a total weighted mean of 4.13, which is interpreted as "Agree." This indicates that respondents generally acknowledge and value the significance and impact of the festival.

Respondents agree that the Bangenge mascots effectively represent the intended characters (WM = 4.00), indicating that the visual elements of the festival are successful in giving cultural identity. The highest weighted mean was observed for the statement indicating that the festival's history still reflects how the Bangenge Festival originated (WM = 4.21), emphasizing a strong recognition of the festival's role in preserving and transmitting local history and traditions.

Respondents also agree that the festival helps them better know the place (WM = 4.16) and offers opportunities for different cultures to interact (WM = 4.09), showing its importance as a cultural and social platform. The festival is also seen as a way to boost the city's tourism industry (WM = 4.16) and motivate both visitors and residents to take part in the event (WM = 4.16), highlighting its role in promoting tourism growth and fostering community involvement.

The materials used in creating the mascots are seen as effective in attracting participation (WM = 4.12), and respondents expressed willingness to recommend the event to others (WM = 4.12). These results indicate that the Bangenge Festival is well accepted and plays an important role in cultural preservation, promoting tourism, and fostering community interaction.

Table 3. Recommendations in Promoting the Bangenge Festival (N = 31)

Classification of Tourist	Frequency	Percentage
Promote the festival in another location.	14	45.16%
Have competition that involves schools and other institutions.	12	38.71%
Launch a YouTube channel.	5	16.13%
Promote the festival in social media.	18	58.06%
Total	30	100%

Table 3 describes the recommendations in promoting the Bangenge Festival. The table shows 14 of the respondents are in favor of promoting the festival in another location, and 12 think that having competition that involves schools and other institutions may help promote the Bangenge Festival more. On the other hand, 5 voted in launching a YouTube channel and 18 said that the Bangenge Festival needs to be promoted in social media.

The results indicate that the respondents strongly support modern and community-focused methods for promoting the Bangenge Festival. The high number of respondents supporting social media promotion indicates that digital platforms are seen as the most effective way to reach a broader and younger audience. Social media allows for faster information sharing, visual storytelling, and audience interaction, which are key for promoting cultural festivals in today's context. Organizing competitions that involve schools and other institutions can increase awareness and motivate participation by promoting community involvement and fostering cultural appreciation among young people. Although fewer respondents recommended launching a YouTube channel, this approach may still serve as a supplementary platform for documenting festival activities and preserving cultural heritage. These findings align with other studies that emphasize the significance of digital media and community engagement in enhancing the visibility and sustainability of cultural festivals (Liang et al., 2021; Quinn et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Based on the gathered data, the majority of the respondents are female with age ranging from 20 years old and below. All are single with most of them answering 'not applicable' when asked about the monthly income. Most of the respondents agreed that the mascot of the Bangenge Festival represents the intended character. The respondents also agreed that the said festival still promotes its history and its location. Most of the respondents agreed that the Bangenge Festival provides opportunities regarding different cultures to interact with one another. This implies that the respondents are likely to recommend the Bangenge Festival.

The researchers suggest that they do not have to look at the accuracy of the design because the point that they can identify the intended character is enough reason to agree and appreciate the creativity of making Bangenge mascots.

The researchers recommend for the municipal of Cavite City to share the history of Bangenge Festival through social media to create a festival community and by publishing helpful information and video content about how it became a tradition for Bangenge makers in the city every Christmas season, so that more people will know more about the origin of the Bangenge Festival.

The researchers further recommend the municipal office of Cavite City to launch a site that is solely dedicated to the festival. Since the festival is less known, this will help emphasize the place and create awareness that such a festival exists. Through the site, more people will know about the festival, its purpose and importance. This will also help boost the tourism of Cavite City.

The researchers recommend building/creating a tourist information center. This will help create an engaging and amicable relationship between locals and tourists. Furthermore, the municipal office of Cavite City is recommended to create seminars/webinars regarding the positive impacts of accepting tourists in the locality. Through this, the locals will be more open and welcoming in accepting tourists and their cultures.

To strengthen tourism, the researchers recommend the invitation of famous artists/influencers to attend the said festival to attract tourists or gain more attractions and create cultural image in the host city by holding the said festivals in the community settings. Specifically, the success of a festival helps attract large crowds, thus strengthening the attractiveness of city, community or tourism destinations.

The researchers recommend the creation of competitions related to the event such as a photo contest. This will encourage the locals and tourists to be more participative and engage in the activities related to the event. Furthermore, this will serve as an opportunity to gain market exposure not only for the Bangenge Festival but for the entire locality.

The researchers suggest the creation of awareness regarding the materials used in making Bangenge mascots. This may be done through seminar/webinars or leaflets explaining the purpose of using such materials in the creation of the mascots. Through this initiative, visitors will be more aware of the reasons behind and history of the mascots.

The researchers recommend the creation of competitions related to the event such as a photo contest. This will encourage the locals and tourists to be more participative and engage in the activities related to the event. Furthermore, this will serve as an opportunity to gain market exposure not only for the Bangenge Festival but for the entire locality.

The researchers recommend possible programs and activities such as promoting the Bangenge Festival in other locations, launching a YouTube channel, promoting the event on social media and having online competitions involving schools and other institutions. The researchers recommend making further improvement in terms of collecting data and bigger sample size to gather more information and make it credible. The researchers also encourage the local residents of Cavite City to attend and participate in the celebration of the Bangenge Festival. This will help instill pride, understanding and love to the one's town. Through their participation, they may become a reliable source of first-hand information about the festival and the importance of the celebration to the company. The researchers encourage the Local Government Unit of Cavite City to promote the cultural well-being of Cavite City regarding the Bangenge Festival and its involvement in tourism. This will support the festival to be well known and can give knowledge to the tourists to know more about the said Festival.

Tourists are encouraged to attend the celebration of the Bengenge Festival. The celebration may give them a unique kind of festival through its main characters, the Bangenge Mascots. The researchers recommended to the tourism students to attend the Bangenge Festival to see how the festival is celebrated; further recommendations by the researchers to read more about the festival for further understanding. As future tourism professionals, they may create tour packages that will include Bangenge Festival in their itinerary. Through this initiative, the festival will be known to a lot of tourists. The researchers recommend for future researchers to read more about the festival. The researchers also suggest immersing themselves by attending the said festival for first-hand information.

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